

THE POLICY OF THE SOVIET GOVERNMENT IN UZBEKISTAN TOWARDS RELIGIOUS INSTITUTIONS AND RELIGIOUS SCHOLARS

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Abstract: This article talks about the policy of the Soviet authorities in Uzbekistan in the 1920s and 1930s in relation to religious authorities and religious scholars.

Key words: khanates, repression, authoritarian regime, communist ideology, central committee.

Since the Middle Ages, for thousands of years, the religion of Islam and its role have occupied an important place in the social, cultural, educational and economic life of the region where we live. In the second half of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century, when the historical processes took place very sharply, in the Bukhara Emirate, Khiva, Kokand khanates, a large part of the land and property belonged to religious institutions and organizations, and they were called waqf land and property.

During the Soviet period, the spiritual and cultural life of our people was put under the grip of communist ideology. The national, spiritual values and traditions of the Uzbek people were violated, and the Uzbek language was turned into a secondary language. The most advanced representatives of the nation, intellectuals were repressed.

Despite the tyranny of the authoritarian regime, there have been positive and creative things in our country. With the selfless work of our people, many cities were built, factories and factories were built, and millions of hectares of new land were developed. Schools, higher and secondary special educational institutions were opened, cultural and spiritual institutions were established, significant achievements were made in the field of science, literature and art.[1]

It is known that Turkestan became a colony of the Russian Empire, and since the rule and policy of foreign rulers started to operate in this area, its oppressed and victimized peoples were deprived of their will and freedom. They became subject to I. Even the last governor-general of Turkestan, A. Kuropatkin, admitted that: "For 50 years, we restrained the indigenous people from development, kept them away from schools and Russian life." However, it is a fact that the naturally proud people of this country never accepted their helpless fate and agreed to live under

the control of others, but on the contrary, their own free will, national independence who fought valiantly on the way. Tomaris, Shiroq, Spitamen, Muqanna, Jalaluddin Manguberdi, Temur Malik, Sheikh Najmiddin Kubro, Mahmud Torabi, Mavlonzada, Abubakr Kalavi, Amir Temur, Muhammadali Eshon, who have taken a worthy place among the jewels of our ancient history, whose dear names have been forever sealed. Dukchi Eshon), Namozbotir Pirimkulov, and the outstanding bravery shown in the difficult historical processes, which have fallen upon the nation, are a living witness to this.[1]

After the establishment of the Communist Party of Turkestan and its Central Committee, its influence on the events and changes in the country's life became stronger. On top of that, the formation of this party as an integral part of the RKP(b), its operation in obedience to all its leadership instructions and orders allowed the leaders of the Center to control the entire situation in Turkestan. Although the Soviet government operating in Turkestan was composed of representatives of two parties - the Bolsheviks and the leftists, this system did not last long. By the beginning of March 1919, under the pressure of the Bolsheviks of the country, the representatives of the works were deprived of the structure of the local Soviet government, which was a clear proof of this. On top of that, the creation of organizations such as the Emergency Bodies or the Committee of the Poor in order to fight against various "counter-revolutionary" enemy forces and foreign elements threatening the Soviet power could not help but have a negative impact on this process. Because such bodies with unlimited powers acted on behalf of the Soviet authorities in the application of harsh punishment measures, and if necessary, they also performed the tasks of the authorities - the Soviets. This, of course, caused the local Soviets of Workers', Peasants' and Soldiers' Deputies to protest. By the spring of 1919, temporary revolutionary committees were established and operated as emergency bodies within the soviets of Muslim workers in Andijan, Namangan, and Margilan regions of the country. By the middle of 1919, such bodies were established in many cities and rural areas of Turkestan.[2]

This stupidity of the executioners of the established regime cannot be justified by anything. This dark darkness of our recent national history has become an eternal dream in the language of our people. It only came to the surface full of national independence, and the citizens of our country were lucky enough to see real light. Repression of intellectuals. The healthy forces of the society, the national intelligentsia, suffered the most from the Stalinist political repression, and gave unparalleled victims. Because the officials of the totalitarian regime are rich

ignorant people, instead of valuing and honoring the people of knowledge and enlightenment, they humiliate, humiliate and, if necessary, destroy them. they took Therefore, from time to time, it became common for them to put intellectuals through the battle cry, to keep their ranks "unified". For example, Munawar Qori, who devoted his whole life and work to miflat happiness and the future of the country, became an innocent victim of the provocation and slander of the Soviets, which escalated during this period. Under his leadership, a trial was organized against 87 members of the "National Independence" organization, which worked for the development and independence of the nation and spread harm to the people. 49 of them were accused of being "enemies of the people" and "bourgeois nationalists" and sentenced to severe punishments. The rulers of the established regime set themselves the goal of destroying the representatives of Jadidism, who dedicated themselves to enlightening the national consciousness and thinking of the Uzbek people, and promoting their identity. They achieved it.[3] People who were sent to study abroad on the initiative and efforts of the government of Uzbekistan in the 20s and became good experts and scientists became victims of deliberate massacre. If they were educated in Germany or Turkey, they were accused of being spies of those countries. For this reason, if a book printed abroad was found during the search in their house, it was enough evidence. After all, if they studied in foreign universities, it was natural that they would have such books. The oppressors of the cruel system escalated their illegal behavior and tried to take control of all the processes of every person, from walking - standing, daily activities, behavior to how he thinks. aspirants. The main purpose of this was to curb people's will and will, to keep it within certain limits, and in this way not to tarnish the honor of the corrupt system, to preserve and preserve its false reputation. [4]

The Soviets treated with cruelty the slightest deviation from their policy. As a result of this, the Soviet ideology, which waged a fierce struggle to subjugate people's worldview, faith, and form it in the spirit of communist ethics, scientific and atheistic principles, caused incalculable damage to the spiritual life of the working people of the republic. In this way, the entire caste of the chief priests, who made an important contribution to the spiritual life of the people for centuries, was destroyed. During this period, condemning a person and branding him as an "enemy of the people" was like "making insurance out of dough" for the oppressors. There were even such cases that during the search of many houses in the republic, if a book printed in Arabic script was found, the owner of that house

was called a stranger to the society without asking about its name and content. He was branded 'nat' and sentenced to prison or exile.

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